

A Comparative Analysis of Acoustic Absorbers for Automotive Application

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Abstract:

The sound absorption (acoustic) properties of nonwovens are reported in this study. Acoustic properties of three different types of nonwovens, namely, layered spunlaced, needle-punched and chemically bonded layers of needle-punched and spunlaced nonwovens were compared with commercial samples. Effects of types of layering, web bonding techniques and pore characteristics were investigated on normal incidence sound absorption behaviour of nonwovens. Pore size and its distribution were measured, and structures of the samples were observed under the scanning electron microscope. The result indicates that by selecting appropriate technologies lighter nonwovens can be developed with improved acoustic properties. A three-layer spunlaced nonwovens (800 g/m² and 3.39 mm thickness) showed a statistically significant improvement in acoustic coefficient (α). The three-layer spunlaced nonwovens α was 0.42 as compared to a 0.22 of the commercial sample (1200 g/m² and 6.09 mm thickness) in the overall frequency range of 50–5700 Hz

Keywords: Acoustic, layering, nonwovens, pore size, sound absorption

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1. Introduction

There are many factors affects the weight of the vehicle in automotive applications. Higher the weight of the vehicle, higher will be the fuel consumption. Therefore, any effort to reduce the weight of the vehicles will going to improve the fuel efficiency. Textile fabrics in various forms used in the automotive applications. Nonwovens contributes a major portion of the textile materials, contributing around 50% [1]. They are used as carpets, roof liners, rear parcel tray, door lines, engine insulators etc [1-5]. Porous materials in the form of nonwovens are used for sound absorption/acoustic applications [1-5].

There are many papers published to improve the acoustic properties [2-3 & 6-13]. In all these published papers, this improvement is linked to increasing the weight and thickness of the nonwovens. Since in automotive applications, these two parameters play a crucial role in improving acoustic properties, any effort to reduce the weight and thickness of the nonwovens without compromising acoustic properties will contribute to the design and manufacturing of new type of products. To achieve it, one of the ways is to combine different nonwoven manufacturing techniques. Most practical approach would be chemical bonding different types of nonwoven products (needle punched, spun laced fabrics etc.) in the form of a layered combination. Sound wave is a form of energy. In order to achieve a good acoustic property, these waves must be dissipated through the fibrous structures. Different layer combination creates different

types of structures. Advantages of a layered combination will be, creating a micro-macro fibrous structure for increasing dissipation of the sound wave within it and thereby, improving acoustic properties. Simultaneously, reduction in weight and thickness can be achieved by these multi-layered products. Factors like fibre types and processing parameters affect the acoustic properties of nonwovens [2-13]. However, very limited research work was published in relating pore size and its distribution with the acoustic properties [2, 4 & 11, 14]. In one study, researchers studied the influence of different fibre combinations and nonwoven manufacturing techniques on acoustic properties [5]. One of their findings was low sound absorbing properties [1, 2] of the spun laced nonwovens [5]. None of these studies reported the relationship between pore characteristics and acoustic properties. Furthermore, there is also lack of information around designing light weight and thinner material with better acoustic properties.

In view of the above background information, the aim was to develop lightweight nonwovens with better acoustic properties and compare them with the commercial samples (floor carpets) particularly, covering the 1/3 octave frequency range from 50–5700 Hz. One of the major acoustic absorber/barrier components in a car compartment is the floor carpets [10]. Acoustic properties of three different types of nonwovens, namely, layered spunlaced (SL), needle-punched (NP) and chemically bonded (CB) layers of NP and SL were studied. The influence of various types of layering and web bonding techniques were investigated on acoustic properties of the nonwovens. Pore characteristics were measured and their relationships with the acoustic properties of the nonwovens have been studied. Structures of the samples were observed under the scanning electron microscope (SEM) to see the influence of chemical bonding on acoustic properties.

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2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Sample preparation

Polyester microfibrils (PETM) were used for producing nine experimental samples. The fibre specifications were linear density 0.9 dtex and staple length 38 mm with silicone spin finish. The commercial reference samples (C1-1000 and C2-1200) were a combination of polyester and recycled shoddy fibres [5]. Sample specifications are shown in Table 1. The areal weight of the samples was maintained at 800 and 900 g/m².

The process parameters on needle-punching for producing individual layers were feeding speed 0.64 m/min, depth of

needle penetration 5 mm, stroke frequency 198 stroke/min, output speed 1.30 m/min. Once individual layers were prepared, all three-layers were combined by needle-punching on both sides at a depth of needle penetration of 4 mm.

The manifold pressure on spunlacing for individual layers were 10, 200, 200 bars for 1st, 2nd and 3rd jet head, respectively. Once the individual layers were prepared by using above parameters, the same parameters were used to combine three individual layers into a sandwiched product. Chemical bonding was carried at 200°C by using the hot melt adhesive, diphenylmethane-4,4'-diisocyanate.

Table 1- Specification of samples, preparation and physical properties

Sample code	Number of layers	Layer sequence			Web bonding technology	Areal density (g/m ²)	Thickness (mm)
		T	B	M			
A1-800	3 layers PETM	SL	SL	SL	Spunlacing	800	3.39
A2-800	3 layers PETM	NP	NP	NP	Needle-punching	800	6.08
A3-800	2 layers sandwich of SL and NP fabrics	SL		NP	Chemical bonding	800	5.08
A4-800	3 layers sandwich SL/ NP/SL	SL	NP	SL	Chemical bonding	800	4.90
A5-800	3 layers sandwich NP/ SL/SL	NP	SL	SL	Chemical bonding	800	4.26
A1-900	3 layers PETM	SL	SL	SL	Spunlacing	900	4.43
A3-900	2 layers sandwich SL and NP	SL		NP	Chemical bonding	900	5.63
A4-900	3 layers sandwich SL/ NP /SL	SL	NP	SL	Chemical bonding	900	6.86
A5-900	3 layers sandwich NP/SL/SL	NP	SL	SL	Chemical bonding	900	5.23
C1-1000	2 layers sandwich of NP	NP		NP	Chemical bonding	1000	4.34
C2-1200	2 layers sandwich of NP	NP		NP	Chemical bonding	1200	6.09

T: Top layer, M: Middle layer, B: Bottom layer.

2.2 Measurement of acoustic properties

ASTM E 1050-19 standard test method was used for measuring acoustic coefficient (α) by using LMS acoustic testing instrument and the frequency range was 50–5700 Hz [15-16]. The frequency range further classified into low (50–1000 Hz), medium (1000–2000 Hz) and high (2000–5700 Hz) ranges.

2.3 Measurement of pore size and its distribution

The pore structure of nonwovens was measured by capillary flow porometer (PMI, model CFP-1100-AEXCC) [14, 17]. Pore size distribution indicates the frequency of distribution of various pore types in a nonwoven structure. Most of the functionality of the nonwovens is dependent upon mean pore diameter. It was the diameter of most of the pores.

2.4 Nonwoven structure

For characterizing structure of the nonwovens, SEM FEI Quanta 200 was used, and samples were sputter coated. Both

longitudinal and cross-sectional images were obtained for the samples. A 20 KV voltage was used during SEM imaging stage.

2.5 Thickness and areal density

EDANA WSP 120.6.R0 (23) was used for thickness measurement [18]. ASTM D 3776M-20 was used for measuring the areal densities [19].

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Influence of different layers, web bonding technology and areal density on acoustic properties

Influence of different layers, areal density and web bonding technology on acoustic properties is shown in Table 2. Majority of the experimental samples showed an improved α values in the overall frequency range (50–5700 Hz) when comparing with reference samples (C1-1000 and C2-1200). Since objective of this work was to develop lighter and thinner nonwovens with better acoustic properties as compared to commercial samples, α value of the samples A1-

800 and C1-1000 and C2-1200 were compared. In terms of α values in (50-5700 Hz) range, sample A1-800 showed a 33% increase over C1-1000 (48% increase over C2-1200). This increase in α value was statistically significant at 95% confidence interval (F-value of the single factor ANOVA test was 193.505). Similar improvements were observed in the medium (1000–2000 Hz) and high frequency (2000–5700 Hz) ranges.

In the low frequency range (50–1000 Hz), α values were comparable. The reason for such improvement in α value could be due to three-layer spunlaced structure. The bonding of the layers had been achieved by mechanical bonding only and without any chemical. It allows a layer-by-layer absorption of the sound. The kinetic energy of the incident sound wave was converted into low level of heat energy as it passed through one to other layers in three-layer structure and resulting in better acoustic properties. The chemical bonding in between the needle-punched layers of the commercial samples (C1-1000 and C2-1200) were impeding the passage of sound wave, resulting in backward reflectance of the sound wave [2].

The longitudinal SEM images of the samples A1-800 and C1-1000 showed smaller pore sizes for the former as compared to the later which also improved the acoustic properties (Figure 1a and Figure 1b). The cross-sectional SEM images of the sample A1-800 is showing a three-layer structure without the use of chemical binders in bonding the layers (Figure 1c). The cross-sectional SEM image of the commercial sample (C1-1000) is showing a two-layer structure with the use of chemical binders in bonding the layers (Figure 1d). Furthermore, lower thickness for sample A1-800 as compared to C1-1000 is visible from the cross-sectional SEM images (Figure 1c and Figure 1d). The thickness of the sample A1-800 was 21% lower than that of the commercial sample (C1-1000) and it was 20% (200 gram) lighter than the commercial sample (C1-1000). By comparing with the other commercial sample (C2-1200), thickness of the sample A1-800 was 44% lower, and it was 33% (400 gram) lighter. Above results showed that it was possible to obtain better acoustic property for light weight and thinner materials by proper selection of material, processing parameters and bonding technology.

Table 2- Acoustic coefficients (a) in various frequency ranges

Sample code	50–1000 Hz	1000–2000 Hz	2000–5700 Hz	50–5700 Hz
A1-800	0.10	0.17	0.53	0.42 (0.019)*
A2-800	0.21	0.60	0.90	0.73 (0.063)
A3-800	0.12	0.30	0.65	0.53 (0.029)
A4-800	0.13	0.28	0.27	0.54 (0.052)
A5-800	0.09	0.24	0.33	0.33 (0.035)
A1-900	0.09	0.22	0.49	0.32 (0.023)
A3-900	0.16	0.59	0.67	0.59 (0.043)
A4-900	0.17	0.44	0.58	0.57 (0.027)
A5-900	0.11	0.30	0.30	0.27 (0.026)
C1-1000	0.12	0.10	0.39	0.28 (0.020)
C2-1200	0.05	0.10	0.30	0.22 (0.015)

*Values in the parenthesis indicate the standard deviations

Figure 1- Longitudinal SEM images of the samples: a. A1-800, b. C1-1000, and cross-sectional images of the samples: c. A1-800, and d. C1-1000.

Comparing α value amongst all samples, sample A1-800 was the best, followed by samples A3-900, A4-900 and A4-800, respectively (Table 2). Sample A2-800 had a α value of 0.73, which was mainly because of the three-layer needle-punched structure and thickness of this sample was the second highest amongst the lot studied. As the sound wave pass from one layer thickness to another, there were frictional loss between the fibres and sound wave [2-3, 5]. Thickness of the sample was playing a role in absorbing the sound wave. Thicker structure was providing a higher frictional loss and resulting in better acoustic properties. Furthermore, there was no chemical bond in between the component layers, which assisted the sound wave to propagate through the structure without impedance.

By comparing the rest of the samples A3-900, A4-900 and A4-800, the two-layer sandwich of spunlaced and needle-punched nonwovens in sample A3-900 provided a finer structure at the surface and coarser structure at the back (Figure 2a and 2b). The finer structure with a greater number of pores in a given area was a result of the spunlacing technology and coarser (loose) structure was a result of the needle-punching technology. The combination of fine and coarse structures helps in improving acoustic properties. Furthermore, there was only chemical bond between the constituent layers. Samples A4-900 and A4-800 was three-layer sandwich of spunlaced/needle-punched/spunlaced, with variable areal densities and thickness. The components of the samples were bonded together by two chemical bonds amongst the layers. It may create obstacle for the absorption of the sound wave, resulting in lower α value (50–5700 Hz) than that for the samples A3-900 and A2-800 [2]. These results suggest that three-layer structures without chemical bonding were performing better than the two-layer structures.

The chemical bonding in between various types of nonwoven layers should be applied with caution, otherwise the final product provides poor acoustic properties [2]. Although 100% needle-punched nonwoven sample (A2-800) showed a better α value (50–5700 Hz), as compared to 100% spunlaced nonwoven (A1-800) and rest of the chemically bonded samples, where space requirement was a major criterion, the spunlaced nonwoven can be an alternative, otherwise, the needle-punched can be used as an acoustic absorber.

In cases, α value increases for higher areal densities (comparing samples A3-800 with A3-900 and A4-800 with A4-900). These increases in α value were statistically significant at 95% confidence interval (Table 3). Standard deviations in α value (50–5700 Hz) for A1-800, A3-800, A4-800 and A5-800 were 0.019, 0.029, 0.052 and 0.035, respectively. Similarly, standard deviations in α value for A1-900, A3-900, A9-800 and A5-900 were 0.023, 0.043, 0.027 and 0.026, respectively. The reason for increase in the α values for the lower areal density samples might be due to reaching threshold values, after which increasing the weight of the material does not improve the acoustic properties. Other factor may be the pore size and its distribution which is discussed in the following section. Similarly, for the materials in higher areal densities, the thickness of the materials was the major factor in deciding the acoustic property. As expected, all samples showed lowest acoustic properties at low frequencies (50–1000 Hz) and highest acoustic properties at higher frequencies (2000–5700 Hz) [10].

Table 3- ANOVA between two different areal densities series on overall acoustic properties (frequency range of 50–5700 Hz)

Summary				
Groups	Count	Sum	Average	Variance
A1-800	5	2.11	0.422	0.00037
A2-800	5	3.66	0.732	0.00407
A3-800	5	2.67	0.534	0.00088
A4-800	5	2.71	0.542	0.00277
A5-800	5	1.64	0.328	0.00127
A1-900	5	1.62	0.324	0.00053
A3-900	5	2.96	0.592	0.00187
A4-900	5	2.85	0.57	0.00075
A5-900	5	1.37	0.274	0.00068

ANOVA						
Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value	F crit
Between Groups	0.920738	8	0.115092	78.53146	1.85E-20	2.208518
Within Groups	0.05276	36	0.001466			
Total	0.973498	44				

Figure 2- Longitudinal SEM images of the sample A3-900: a. spunlacing side, and b. needle-punching side

3.2 Influence of pore size and its distribution on acoustic properties

Influence of various pore sizes on acoustic properties of the nonwovens is shown in Table 4. The mean pore sizes were ranging from 15.885–47.602 μm for the experimental samples and 32.797–36.620 μm for the commercial reference samples. Smaller pore size helps in dampening the effect of sound wave by offering higher frictional resistance to the passage of sound wave. The minimum and maximum values of the pore sizes were the two extreme values ranging from 3.262–7.839 μm and 21.248–86.687 μm , respectively.

Table 4- Size and types of pores and porosity of the samples

Sample code	Minimum (μm)	Mean flow (μm)	Maximum (μm)	Porosity
A1-800	3.482	16.702 (1.690)*	43.211	0.828
A2-800	7.443	43.448 (5.331)	81.153	0.904
A3-800	7.826	47.602 (3.731)	82.887	0.885
A4-800	5.743	44.231 (6.121)	86.687	0.881
A5-800	5.163	20.147 (2.770)	25.124	0.863
A1-900	4.154	15.885 (1.278)	40.013	0.852
A3-900	7.839	17.370 (1.978)	37.330	0.884
A4-900	3.663	17.845 (1.879)	21.248	0.904
A5-900	5.740	27.293 (2.854)	30.229	0.874
C1-1000	3.262	32.797 (3.863)	53.546	0.845
C2-1200	5.317	36.620 (4.56)	98.365	0.856

*Values in the parenthesis indicate the standard deviations.

By comparing the mean flow pore sizes of the samples A1-800, A1-900, C1-1000 and C2-1200 as per the objectives of the work to obtain better acoustic properties for light weight and thinner materials, not much difference in the pore sizes of samples A1-800 and A1-900 was noticed. The mean pore sizes of the commercial samples (C1-1000 and C2-1200) were double than that of the samples A1-800 and A1-900. In terms of α value (50–5700 Hz), A1-800 was the best, followed by A1-900, C1-1000 and C2-1200. The pore size distribution of these samples is shown in Figure 3a. Sample A1-800 showed a uniform pore size distribution in comparison to A1-900 and C1-1000 and C2-1200. Uniform distribution of the pore size was greatly assisting in dampening the sound wave, resulting in better acoustic properties. Although mean pore sizes of the samples A1-800 and A1-900 were almost similar, their pore size distributions were different. This difference in pore size distributions was translated into their respective acoustic behaviours, where

sample A1-800 shows a better acoustic result in comparison with A1-900 in the overall frequency 50–5700 Hz range. Similarly, samples C1-1000 and C2-1200 showed wider pore size distribution as compared to the samples A1-800 and A1-900, which resulted in lower α value for both of them.

Figure 3- Pore size and its distribution for samples: a. A1-800, A1-900, C1-1000 and C2-1200, b. A5-800 and A5-900, c. A2-800 and A4-800

By considering an example of comparing the mean flow pore sizes of samples A5-800 and A5-900, better acoustic properties of A5-800 can be explained in terms of its smaller mean flow pore sizes along with a uniform pore size distribution as compared to the sample A5-900 (Figure 3b). Uniform distribution of the pore size improves the acoustic performance.

Similarly, considering another example by comparing the mean flow pore sizes of samples A2-800 and A4-800, was not much difference between the pore sizes of samples was noticed (Figure 3c). α value (50–5700 Hz) of A2-800 was significantly higher than that of A4-800. The reason could be better and uniform pore size distribution in the case of sample A2-800 as compared to sample A4-800 which resulted in

such high α value for sample A2-800. Of course, other factors such as the type of nonwoven bonding technology and layering also play a role in determining the acoustic behaviour. All the above cases confirm that pore size alone cannot be a concluding factor in achieving desired acoustic properties and the effect of pore size distribution should be also considered.

Figure 4- Relationship between mean pore size and acoustic properties (50–5700 Hz) for 800 g/m² areal density series

The porosity of various types of nonwovens is shown in Table 4. More porous area means that it allows the passage of sound wave through the structure [4], which is a basic requirement for developing acoustic properties in a nonwoven. Further reduction in the sound wave depends

upon various factors like type of bonding, layering, as discussed in the preceding sections. A regression analysis has been carried out for the samples of 800 g/m² areal densities to establish the relationship between mean pore size and acoustic properties (50–5700 Hz). A good correlation between pore size and acoustic properties ($R^2 = 0.84$) was observed (Figure 4).

4. Conclusion

Acoustic properties of layered spunlaced, needle-punched and chemical bonded nonwoven structures were investigated. Best results were shown by a three-layer needle-punched nonwoven with α value of 0.73 in the overall frequency range 50–5700 Hz. A light weight three-layer spunlaced nonwovens with 800 g/m² and 3.39 mm thickness showed 0.42 as α value as compared to the commercial sample (1200 g/m² and 6.09 mm thickness), which showed 0.22 as α value in the 50-5700 Hz frequency range. Needle-punched nonwoven showed a better α value (50–5700 Hz) as compared to the spunlaced and rest of the chemical bonded samples. It was possible to achieve better acoustic properties in the overall frequency range for light weight and thinner nonwoven materials. All the samples under study showed lower acoustic properties at low frequencies and higher values at higher frequencies. Pore size alone cannot be a concluding factor in achieving desired acoustic properties and the effect of pore size distribution should be also considered.

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